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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Executive summary

The Survey of existing civil society engagement tools and projects in Research, Innovation, Learning and Teaching is intended to give an overview of Public Engagement practices at the universities of the ENLIGHT Network. This will allow mutual learning and joint development of adapted approaches and stepping up the *Ladder of Participation* from information and one-directional approaches toward more interactive engagement. The results of this survey and the analysis thereof will be made available to the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory and will be updated dynamically.

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This document was discussed with representatives of all ENLIGHT-RISE partners assigned to WP6, their comments taken into account.

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Abbreviations:

ENLIGHT partner	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
National University of Ireland, Galway	NUIG	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE

University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

Introduction

ENLIGHT is a European University Network of nine partners aim that collaborate intensely in research, education, management and outreach. Building on former collaboration and alliances it started in 2020 with an Erasmus+ grant and expands its activities through the ENLIGHT-RISE project which received funding from Horizon 2020's Science with and for Society Programme (see Appendix I for more information on ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT-RISE).

Through ENLIGHT RISE, the ENLIGHT European University alliance seeks to develop common R&I strategies, capitalize on its partners' synergies to deliver on Europe's greatest societal challenges, facilitate the sharing of capacity through unprecedented levels of collaboration, increase its ability to attract and retain talent, co-operate with our surrounding R&I ecosystems, and finally engage citizens in our scientific endeavours.

With this, ENLIGHT aims to achieve a quantum leap in co-creating research and innovation with and for society, both at the level of each university and at the level of the alliance, in order to maximize our impact on society at the local and global level, and to position our university alliance as a trust broker in a responsible DI/AI ecosystem.

Therefore, this work package (WP6) is aimed to foster genuine engagement of civil society actors (citizens, civil society organizations, communities, municipalities, non-profits/3rd sector) in ENLIGHT research and innovation activities (from setting research agendas, to executing the research, analysing and interpreting findings and discussing follow-up and creating impact), thus co-creating knowledge, as well as including students in this collaboration.

We aim to achieve this by setting up a mentoring programme within the ENLIGHT alliance for mobilization and mutual learning and collaboration in genuine engagement of civil society in research and innovation.

The mobilization and mutual learning through mentoring can have the following activities:

- Mutual site visits, presentations to various target groups/stakeholders
- Training sessions (on location/online); webinars
- Executing pilot projects by partners
- Support (supplying materials, tools; responding to questions)
- Survey/Focus Group(s) with stakeholders for evaluation and learning
- Publications/Presentations/Workshops for dissemination

Finally, this should lead to local action plans to institutionalize activities within ENLIGHT partners and to set up connections for conducting research on the same topic in parallel or jointly, to learn and compare, and to exchange approaches and findings (many topics relevant for citizens are reflected in ENLIGHT flagship challenges). This ties in with the ENLIGHT plans to connect students to jointly work on problems defined by civil society, in transdisciplinary settings, but widens it to joint research and innovation activities. We will also establish an action plan to sustain ENLIGHT joint engagement activities with civil society in R&I, by initiating collaboration in larger projects, e.g., larger citizen science projects, by identifying and applying for joint funding.

As a first step, however, we started with an inventory of public engagement activities and structures that ENLIGHT-partners currently have in place.

This report contains the results of this initial survey among ENLIGHT-partners to identify their current civil society engagement tools and projects in Research, Innovation, Learning and Teaching. It aims at supporting the ENLIGHT community in learning about current trends in public engagement among the partner universities as well as provides help as a benchmarking exercise which will allow for future joint development of adapted approaches and stepping up the *Ladder of Participation*¹. It is important to note that this overview is a not necessarily complete snapshot and will be updated throughout the project, i.e. this deliverable is meant as a 'dynamic document'. We are currently investigating how to make results available in a searchable

¹ Originally coined by Shelley Arnstein in 1969 (Arnstein, S.R. (1969). "A ladder of citizen participation". Journal of the American Institute of Planners. 35 (4): 216–224. doi:10.1080/01944366908977225. hdl:11250/2444598), for citizen participation in decision making. Adapted for use in Public Engagement with Research by e.g. the Engage2020 project (see eg Jellema J, Mulder HAJ. Public Engagement in Energy Research. *Energies*. 2016; 9(3):125. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9030125>) and the HEIRRI project (www.ecsite.eu/sites/default/files/9concepts_and_practice_of_responsible_research_and_innovation.zip).

way as well, to facilitate the discovery of the most appropriate examples or identify contact details for collaboration.

Links with other ENLIGHT RISE/ENLIGHT E+ deliverables

As this deliverable is based on a survey used for mapping and benchmarking the Public Engagement practices across the consortium, the results of deliverable D6.1 are closely connected to *D2.2 ENLIGHT R&I Observatory*, which will be an on-line one stop portal centralizing various benchmarking results, surveys and evidence-based policy recommendations emerging from the project. The Observatory will be connected to the ENLIGHT website and will be designed for a broad audience of researchers and (for non-confidential sections) also to non-academic stakeholders of ENLIGHT.

Information from our survey can also be useful for deliverables in WP7, for the Open Science Status Quo & Opportunities (7.1) and the OA & RDM Starter Kit for Researchers (7.2).

As societal engagement is closely linked and is an integral part of impact-driven research and innovation, D6.1 results will be also taken into consideration in Work Package 8 activities and Deliverables. More specifically, D6.1 identified public engagement initiatives will be taken into consideration in D8.1 repository of best practices, and used as reference in Task 8.1.1 training actions on how to engage with non-specialist audiences and policy-makers.

Reading Guide

This document starts with an overview of the concept and scope of *Public Engagement*. It then describes the way the survey was conducted. Some general observations are then described, after which the main findings will be presented in three sections: (1) currently existing structures (i.e. designated units) responsible for public engagement; (2) an overview of existing public engagement activities; and finally (3) an overview of how public engagement is incorporated into ENLIGHT-partners' strategic plans. The document ends with an outlook to the next steps in the work package. Finally, the appendices section is designed to gather information on ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT-RISE, and the questionnaire designed to collect all the information.

What is Public Engagement?

Public Engagement with Research (PER) is an umbrella-term for many different activities to connect research with civil society. We will use the definition as given by the National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCPE) in the UK²:

"Public engagement describes the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit."

The NCCPE further states that *"mutual benefit is an important part of our definition as we are keen to emphasise that high quality public engagement benefits all those involved. Benefits might include learning, developing new skills, gaining new insights or ideas, developing better research, raising aspiration, or being inspired"*.

The main reasons for embarking in PER activities may be:

1. Democratic motive: the public (as tax payer) has a right to know what's happening and to be involved in decision making on research (as research can impact their lives).
2. Instrumental motive: Involving civil actors increases the quality of research and its value to and impact on society, even more so when focusing on solving the grand societal challenges.

PER goes beyond traditional science communication, which tends to focus on *transmitting* research results and scientific knowledge to the public (in order to educate them). Traditional science communication is usually motivated by the fact that well-skilled scientific/technical people can contribute to society and the economy, the public has a right-to-know about publicly funded research (so they can form an opinion and discuss decisions), and to support a scientific culture. Science communication activities are sometimes based on the assumption that the public has a *knowledge deficit*, and more knowledge will make them supportive of new technologies. This, however, is not always the case, and one-way communication does not always close the gap between science and society.

PER is more interactive and focuses on a two-way communication, a dialogue. It comes in many forms, and can be structured on various criteria. It is one of the important elements of *Responsible Research and Innovation* and *Open Science*. In the research process, we can distinguish agenda-setting (select the topic, problem definition/aim, proposal), data collection, data analysis, and drawing conclusion/meaning/implications

² <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/about-engagement/what-public-engagement>

or even implementation of outcomes. Some PER-activities focus on separate phases of the research.

Firstly, PER activities can be arranged according to their level of intensity. This can range from a one-off, informal discussion, without any strings attached, to full collaboration throughout the whole research process. "Genuine" engagement means that researchers respond to the public and the public can have some influence (to various degrees). 'Stepping up the ladder of participation', in this case, means making

collaboration more focused on society's needs and views, and collaborating throughout the research process, as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1.

VARIOUS LEVELS OF PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT, WITH EXAMPLES OF FORMATS (SOURCE: BASED ON ENGAGE2020 PROJECT)

Figure 2 shows the 'ladder' in another format:

FIGURE 2. ANOTHER WAY TO GRAPHICALLY SHOW THE 'LADDER OF PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH'. (SOURCE: HEIRRI-PROJECT).

Secondly, we can distinguish different target groups to collaborate with. See Table 1 (adapted from Engage2020 and Borg, Galema, Mulder & Steenwijk, 2016³). The distinction between various categories is not always very sharp.

Citizens	Citizens in general
- <i>Affected (could include patients, vulnerable groups, etc)</i>	<i>Citizens especially impacted by research outcomes</i>
- <i>Consumers</i>	<i>Citizens in their role of consumer</i>
- <i>Employees</i>	<i>Citizens in their role of employees</i>
- <i>Users</i>	<i>Citizens in their role of (potential) user of a technology</i>
CSOs (civil society organizations)	Organized stakeholders from civil society. Can be formal/informal, small citizens groups to larger NGOs.
Non-profit Organizations	Independent non-profit organizations
Policy-makers	Can be representatives of municipalities, public agencies etc
Pupils/Schools	Different age groups / curricular/extra-curricular
Other specific groups	E.g. journalists, senior citizens, social enterprises, etc

Table 1. Different target groups for Public Engagement (adapted from Engage2020 and Borg, Galema, Mulder & Steenwijk, 2016). Note: Industry is not part of the "public" in Public Engagement. However, for some projects, it may be helpful or even necessary to include industry partners in the discussion or collaboration process of researchers and the public (quadruple helix innovation).

A broad overview of PER-formats for different target groups in various stages of the research project can be found in the Action Catalogue (Engage2020): <http://actioncatalogue.eu>. A glossary is given at the end of this document.

Thirdly, one can distinguish between PER-activities that are not yet embedded, done occasionally by individuals, or project-funded and PER-structures that are embedded in strategic plans, with responsible departments/persons and relatively stable means/funds to execute activities (with a large grey area in-between).

Finally, universities usually have outreach programmes focused on attracting future students (which is an additional incentive for them to employ these activities). These programmes can range from pure marketing to science communication and PER-

³ Borg, H., Galema, A. J. B. E., Mulder, H. A. J. & Steenbeek, S. The University of Groningen: an Engaging University., In: Goddard, J., Hazelkorn, E., Kempton, L. & Vallance, P. (Eds.). (2016). *The Civic University: The Policy and Leadership Challenges*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, blz. 201-221

activities; either focusing very direct on the target groups (final years secondary school) or on younger children and their parents (creating a scientific culture). Parts of these activities could fall under the heading of 'public engagement'.

Method

To get an overview of current Public Engagement activities of the ENLIGHT partners, desk research and a survey were conducted in November 2021-January 2022, fulfilling the following steps:

1. We started with a web search on PE activities mentioned on the institutional websites of the ENLIGHT partners.
2. We created an online survey form, which was tested by 4 people; once finalised, a link was sent to the contact persons of ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT-RISE WP6, with the request to forward it to those involved in PE activities at their organisation. It was accompanied by a document describing PE and the intentions of the work package, and mentioned the activities already found on the websites, and two examples of how the survey could be filled in. Some general and specific reminders were sent in this period.

By the end of January 2022, we had received 79 responses. The data were assessed and coded by two members of the team separately, to get a clear indication of the position of the mentioned activity on the ladder of participation. In case consensus was not reached, follow up questions were posed to those that had filled out the survey forms; in a few cases, short video calls were made with them.

As a result, we have a first overview of PE activities of nine partner universities, with an indication of their position on the ladder of public engagement. Given the definition of Public Engagement, we excluded activities that use the public as a research object and activities that solely focus on university-industry collaboration (so we *do* include activities that engage with *both* industry and the public). We also excluded terminated activities.

As a disclaimer, the reader should consider some limitations of the data collection. Firstly, we are aware that not all contact persons may have had a full overview of who is involved in PE activities at their (large) institutes, so there are for sure many more activities that we are as yet unaware of. We did notice that the survey forms were forwarded occasionally to colleagues by those receiving it (snow balling). As we wanted to get a first overview of main activities we find this an acceptable limitation. We will, however, keep a survey open and continue to collect information, and append this document. A second limitation might have been confusion on what is considered PE

and what is not, despite the information given. However, we attempted to sort out this limitation in our assessment of the filled-out forms.

Apart from an overview of current Public Engagement activities of the ENLIGHT partners, we have also decided to make a strategic plan analysis to find similarities and possible room for improvement amongst the partner universities' Public Engagement practices and plans for the future. The analysis started with a web search of partner websites and a request for strategic plans from each partner university.

We received all the strategic plans by the end of November 2021. The plans were afterwards analysed and compared, whilst considering the ENLIGHT RISE joint approach towards Public Engagement, Research & Innovation communication as well as co-creation with and for society.

We would like to stress that there is no one-way approach towards Public Engagement at universities, therefore our analysis should not be understood as a form of competition, but rather as an opportunity for the consortium to learn with and from each other.

Public Engagement in current strategic plans and links to ENLIGHT/RISE aims

An analysis of the current strategic plans of partner universities was conducted with a focus not only on the above-mentioned public engagement definition but also with consideration of the ENLIGHT RISE objectives/tasks connected to Public Engagement:

- Quadruple Helix activation.
- Development of methodologies that mobilize genuine engagement with civil society in research and innovation.
- Increasing society's trust in science and improvement of the quality of the science for the society concept.

Every university's viewpoint on Public Engagement can be individual, yet they all aim towards the same target. We tried to divide these into separate thematic subgroups to make the analysis comprehensible to the reader. We would like to stress the importance of all the activities and viewpoints. They are all important building stones in creating a stimulating environment for a far-reaching and institutionally and socially embedded public engagement. We would also want to state beforehand that this chapter should be understood as a simple overview of current approaches and a possible inspiration to the nine universities and not as an in-depth synthesis of all the strategic plans.

1. Popularisation

Popularisation fulfils the task of making the research findings accessible, understandable and first and foremost usable for the public. According to our partners, all artistic, cultural, or scientific mediation programs promoting intellectual and cultural wealth should be promoted. The popularisation of scientific and cultural knowledge provides keys for everyone to make their way in a complex world and to become an active player in responsible science ([UBx](#)). Popularisation of research should be promoted as an inseparable part of the career of researchers and teaching as it increases the understanding of the content and objectives of research in society ([UT](#)).

To develop a far-reaching popularisation practice, research results should be distributed in a generally comprehensive manner and thus increase the understanding of research in society ([UT](#)). This could be done either by learning to cooperate with media efficiently, by developing university media channels or by building websites to

showcase the scientific and technological results and capabilities of different research groups ([UPV/EHU](#)).

2. Collaboration

Interdisciplinarity, inter-organizational collaboration within a community or region, and international collaborations enable research improvement by blending scientific approaches, resources, and knowledge. Collaboration between internal stakeholders (students, researcher, staff) and external stakeholders contributes to new innovative research questions and methods. Open collaboration is instrumental to tackle the challenges that society faces nowadays ([RUG](#)).

Collaboration should be understood as an integral part of research and education. Universities should take a proactive coordinated approach to collaboration both to increase the relevance of universities' research and education as well as to make new knowledge usable outside of academia ([UU](#)).

Some partner universities thus work towards stimulating learning and research in an interdisciplinary setting with and for regional, European and global partners to find innovative solutions to societal challenges. It is also possible to identify relevant teaching and research topics in co-operation with social partners ([RUG](#)).

3. Open discussion

Open discussion in Academia is an essential practice to secure that research will be done with and for society -- and thus, regarding the challenges public society currently faces. Research should provide evidence-based solutions to develop state policy ([UT](#)). Universities should encourage cooperation with the public sector in carrying out studies on major societal challenges and co-create a motivating environment for researchers to find solutions for these problems ([UT](#)). This could be reached by building publicly open locations enabling consultations on various topics ([UBx](#)). Open discussion and co-creation should not be set aside under the pretext of reaching consensus being difficult ([UBx](#)).

4. Promotion of a knowledge transfer culture

In this section, we want to highlight methods that our partners apply to make dissemination practices more effective because this topic closely relates to the above-mentioned points. For example, we can see many mentions across the consortium of initiatives that support entrepreneurial skills among PhD students and young

researchers.⁴ There are also new study programmes, dedicated to dissemination practices, knowledge transfer and cooperation with external stakeholders. Other possible, less grand, but still very effective solutions could be various information sessions/workshops/seminars on entrepreneurship, effective dissemination, and knowledge transfer. Cooperation with specialists in this field, along with establishing contacts with local institutions and boosting the number of doctoral theses conducted in collaboration with external stakeholders ([UPV/EHU](#)) can increase knowledge transfer and prepare the ground for the research-culture change at the institution.

5. **Fully integrated engagement and impact into research development and assessment**
6. **A structured programme of engagement for possible partners and researchers**

These two aspects are considered together. To stimulate research with a deep societal value and impact, it is important to define and highlight the impact this type of research has on society. According to some of our partners, this can be achieved by introducing a new approach towards research and dissemination in contrast to the rather classical way of research impact assessment that mainly focused on quantification and output ([UGent](#)). It also means explicitly recognising and rewarding (interdisciplinary) co-operation with external partners and the generation of societal impact ([RUG](#)).

Possible actions at the institutional level that could lead towards more research with a deeper societal value and impact could be:

- Specific web pages to inform researchers. These could contain information on activities in order to create societal value and generate impact, funding opportunities, platforms supporting impact, training opportunities etc.
- A broader understanding of research impact should be a dimension in research evaluations at the institutional level as well as generally
- Changes in proposal requirements and assessment guidelines of funding organisations
- Collection of impact success stories
- Institutional support of citizen science
- Creation and promotion of platforms supporting societal impact ([UGent](#))

⁴ For example [Training programme for PhD candidates](#) or [Career Perspectives Series](#) at Groningen University, [Ghent University Doctoral Training Programme](#), [University of Bordeaux](#), [Research skills training](#) at NUGalway.

- Starting more multi-disciplinary schools ([RUG](#))

It is important to say that cooperation with external stakeholders will significantly contribute to creating societal value and impact. Therefore all informational services regarding impact-driven research at the university as well as collaboration opportunities should always be visible not only to the researcher but also to the general public.

Such a strong emphasis on societal impact requires professional and comprehensive support, with an explicit focus on outreach and public engagement ([RUG](#)).

Current structures and activities in public engagement with research – survey results

In this section, we present a general overview of our findings from the survey on public engagement activities at ENLIGHT partner institutions (see appendix III for the survey questions). We collected 81 responses to the questionnaire (coming from all ENLIGHT partners). Given that two forms described the same activity, we ended up with 79 unique responses. It is important to remember that a survey instrument will be maintained open throughout the project.

Some interesting general findings can be outlined.

Firstly, there is a distinction between projects that are fully embedded and those that are done on a project basis or based on voluntary contributions. About 40% of the activities mentioned were fully embedded in the universities, another 35% were supported by project funding. The remaining 25% were singular activities.

The activity is
81 responses

Secondly, internal actors involved comprised academics in almost all cases. It is interesting to see that about 40% of the activities mentioned that students were involved in public engagement activities as part of their curriculum.

Who are involved internally?

81 responses

On the other hand, diverse external stakeholders were reported as target groups and/or partners:

Who are external target groups/partners

81 responses

Finally, the question on the 'level of engagement' turned out to be quite difficult to answer. In our assessment⁵ we found both underestimation and overestimation compared to our judgement, or just plain 'I don't know'. We also noticed that some respondents provided a mixture of activities for which they filled out one form, or focused on a specific phase of the research.

⁵ Two of the authors individually scored the activities on the level of engagement. Differences were discussed and additional information was acquired from those who had submitted the form if required, after which a consensus was reached about the level of engagement of an activity.

Structures for PE

In this section, we will describe some typical PE structures and activities among the ENLIGHT-RISE partners, including specific organizational units that have a continuous responsibility for public engagement. There are also structural *activities*, such as Science Festivals, that are held regularly; these will be described in the next chapter, with an overview of various (also non-regular or temporary) activities.

It is worth mentioning that the overview is not complete, as after our initial survey we are convinced to be able to identify similar structures in other partner universities.

Museums and Science Centres

A number of ENLIGHT partners have created a museum or a science centre. The latter is distinguished by a focus on the natural sciences and technology, and it uses interactive exhibits. Museums usually cover a wider range of disciplines and also maintain and display collections.

Apart from exhibitions, these museums and science centres commonly implement a range of educational activities (e.g. visiting school classes), and they offer or are involved in various public engagement activities. These usually are at the level of informal dialogue.

University of Groningen has a Science Centre, hosted at the Faculty of Science and Engineering. This has a hands-on exhibition, a mobile Science Centre (Discovery Truck)

and is responsible for many of the public engagement and outreach activities of the faculty.

Some museums, like the Forum Wissen (Knowledge Forum) of the University of Göttingen, also offer cultural spaces, which other universities may offer at other locations.

University	Museum	Science Centre
UBx	meb.u-bordeaux.fr	
UGent	www.gum.gent/	
RUG	www.rug.nl/um	www.rug.nl/sciencelinx/
UPV/EHU	www.ehu.eus/en/web/basque-museum-medicine/home	
NUIG	www.nuigalway.ie/visitorsgeologyum/	
	www.nuigalway.ie/visitorszoologyum/	
	www.nuigalway.ie/visitorscomputerum/	
UT	www.muuseum.ut.ee/	
	www.natum.ut.ee/	
UU	www.uu.se/en/about-uu/culture/museums/	
UGOE	www.forum-wissen.de	

Table 2: Museums in the ENLIGHT-Network (based on web search and initial survey)

Multidisciplinary Schools

A number of ENLIGHT partners have multi- or transdisciplinary research centres that actively collaborate with various stakeholders. Co-creation projects comprise various PE activities in various phases of research. The focus on specific societal challenges seems key for a mutually beneficial collaboration with societal partners.

Our initial survey identified a number of these multidisciplinary schools or research centres, as depicted in Table 2.

University	Department	Topic	Website
UGhent	Interdisciplinary research consortia aimed at realising societal impact	10 different IDCs	www.ugent.be/en/research/science-society/idc/overview.htm
	<i>Henri Pirenne Institute for Medieval Studies</i>	<i>cross-disciplinary research into the medieval period</i>	www.ugent.be/pirenne
	<i>Ghent Centre for Global Studies</i>	<i>critical study of globalisation, with</i>	globalstudies.ugent.be

		<i>special attention to the interaction of global and local processes</i>	
	<i>IDC Crime, Criminology and Criminal Policy</i>	<i>inter-disciplinary on security, crime and deviance related topics in local, national, European and international contexts.</i>	www.ugent.be/crime
	PSYNC	<i>working together for mental health</i>	www.ugent.be/psync/en
	<i>Human Rights Research Network</i>	<i>human rights</i>	hrrn.ugent.be
	<i>GRAY - Ghent University Research for Aging Young</i>	<i>healthy aging</i>	gray.be
	UGent@Work	<i>work and the labour market</i>	www.ugent.be/ugentatwork
	<i>Urban Academy</i>	<i>collaboratorium for sustainability issues in Ghent</i>	destadsacademie.be
	DELTA	<i>Digital innovation for man and society</i>	www.ugentdelta.be
	<i>Centre for the Social Study of Migration and Refugees (CESSMIR)</i>	<i>Migration and Social Mobility: Creating Impact through Participation</i>	www.ugent.be/cessmir/
RUG ⁶	Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health	Public Health	www.rug.nl/aletta/public-engagement/
CU	Academic Research centre for Autism	Autism	acva.sk
	Centre for Active Ageing	Healthy Ageing	www.active-ageing.eu/de/
NUIG	College of Nursing, Medicine and Health Sciences	Public Patient Involvement	www.nuigalway.ie/ppi/

Table 3: Multidisciplinary Research Schools or Centres in the ENLIGHT-Network

⁶ The University of Groningen is currently considering three more multidisciplinary research schools. Wubbo Ockels School focusing on the energy transition and climate adaptation for a sustainable planet; Jantina Tammes School focusing on digital innovation, artificial intelligence, and technological progress for a knowledge-based society; Rudolf Agricola School focusing on governance, politics and sustainable processes to realise a sustainable society.

Science Shops

A few ENLIGHT partners have Science Shops or similar facilities for Civil Society Organizations to have research done on their demand. In this co-creation process, often students are involved as part of their curriculum. The research project is defined together, based on the CSOs needs. The CSO can have varying degrees of involvement in the actual research process. The results of the research are made public. The service is usually free of charge and students do the research as part of their curriculum.

NUI Galway has a centralized unit, working across the university. It is part of the larger unit called [Community Knowledge Initiative](#), which also facilitates Service Learning.

At University of Groningen there is a de-centralized system, where there are five faculty-based Science Shops instead of a central office (to be closer to staff and students). There is a partnership with other stakeholders in a sixth, joint Science Shop (WIJS). There is also a Law Shop, which differs a bit, as it does not do research, but gives (telephonic) advise on legal issues.

UGent currently has a 'light' version of a Science Shop, where a website allows connections between organizations with questions and students/course units; UGent is currently looking into expanding this into a genuine Science Shop⁷.

The University of the Basque Country's Sustainability Office offers a similar service, where students do projects for societal organizations in Latin America.

⁷ which could then be part of wetenschapswinkel.be, currently a collaboration of VU Brussels, University of Antwerp and Catholic University Leuven.

University	Facility	Link
UGent	Call for Challenges	www.callforchallenges.be/en
RUG <i>Faculty of Science & Engineering</i> <i>Faculty of Philosophy</i> <i>University Medical Centre Groningen</i> <i>Faculty of Arts</i> <i>Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences</i>	Science Shops <i>Beta Science Shop</i>	www.rug.nl/wewi www.rug.nl/society-business/science-shops/beta-wetenschapswinkel
	<i>Knowledge Centre Philosophy</i>	www.rug.nl/filosofie/outreach
	<i>Science Shop for Medicine & Public Health</i>	www.rug.nl/society-business/science-shops/geneeskunde-en-volksgesondheid
	<i>Science Shop for Language, Culture and Communication</i>	www.rug.nl/society-business/science-shops/taal-cultuur-en-communicatie
	<i>Science Shop for Education Studies</i>	www.rug.nl/society-business/science-shops/gedrag-en-maatschappij
	<i>WIJS - connecting student & society (collaboration with Hanze University, Municipality, Social Work Teams, Vocational Schools)</i>	wijsgroningen.nl
<i>Faculty of Law</i>	<i>Law Shops</i>	www.rug.nl/rechten/recht-en-samenleving/advies-of-hulp/
UPV/EHU	Sustainability Office: Gaztenpatia	www.ehu.eus/en/web/oficop/gaztenpatia
NUIG	Engaging People in Communities: EPIC	www.nuigalway.ie/cki/epic/

Table 4: Science Shops and similar in the ENLIGHT-Network

Units organizing public engagement events

Partners have a variety of departments that are responsible to organize public engagement events, such as public lectures, informal dialogues, Science Cafés, and Science Festivals. Apart from the role of museums and science centres in this, we have found the following structures.

At University of Bordeaux the *Cultural Services Department* organizes various activities, including e.g. Science Cafés. University of Groningen organizes these and other public lectures through its *Studium Generale* department. At the University of Ghent this task is allocated to the *Science Communication Unit*.

At University of Göttingen, these activities are coordinated by the *Public Relations Department*, including events like Nacht des Wissens (Night of Science). At University of Ghent this department also organizes events and dialogues, like Science Cafés.

The University of the Basque has established a *Chair of Scientific Culture of the UPV/EHU and Euskampus Fundazioa*, which is very active in science communication and public engagement.

University	Structure	Link
UBx	cultural services department	www.u-bordeaux.fr/Recherche/Mediation-scientifique/Les-Rencards-du-savoir
UGent	Science Communication Unit	www.ugent.be/nl/onderzoek/maatschappij/wetenschapscommunicatie
RUG	Studium Generale	sggroningen.nl/
UPV/EHU	Chair of Scientific Culture of the UPV/EHU and Euskampus Fundazioa	zientzia.info/en/sobre-la-catedra/
UGOE	Public Relations Department / Third Mission division	www.uni-goettingen.de/en/620547.html

Table 5: Units in the ENLIGHT-Network responsible for Public Engagement Events

Organizations supporting formal and informal education

A few partners have reported organizations responsible for outreach activities for schools and pupils (from elementary schools to high schools), in addition to the role that museums and science centres have in this. These activities can comprise making materials for teachers, offering guest lectures or advice or facilities for pupils.

University of Groningen has a *Scholieren Academie (Schools Students/Pupils Academy)*, which e.g. offers three Support Points for high school students and has the *Science Node*, maintaining connections with primary schools.

In our survey, we found two organizations offering public courses for specific target groups, such as elderly. Comenius University does this through their *University of the Third Age*, University of Groningen has a *Seniors Academy*.

University	Other Structures	Link
RUG	Scholierenacademie	www.rug.nl/society-business/scholierenacademie/
	Senior Academy	www.rug.nl/society-business/knowledge-and-learning/short-courses-and-public-lectures/senior-academy
CU	University of the Third Age	cdv.uniba.sk/en/university-of-the-third-age/about-us

Table 6: Units in the ENLIGHT-Network supporting (in)formal education

Green Offices

Various universities operate a Green Office, sometimes as part of a larger structure. These Green Offices usually engage with the wider academic community (faculty, students, support staff) and stakeholders on Campus. As such, their projects can be of a collaborative nature.

ENLIGHT Regional Academies

As part of the ENLIGHT-Erasmus+ Project, ENLIGHT-partners will organize so-called *Regional Academies*. These resemble to a certain extent the structures like the Multidisciplinary Research Schools and Science Shops, but they are currently in a pilot phase. Challenge-based *ENLIGHT Living Labs* will be organised hosted by the ENLIGHT Regional Academies, bringing together transdisciplinary groups of students and academics, companies and business incubators, governments, policy makers and citizens. Together they will work on solutions for complex challenges as they emerge locally. The Living Labs will serve as an incubator for other research-driven initiatives along each flagship domain: project-based short programmes, joint programmes, the ENLIGHT doctoral network and new research and innovation activities that will aid the implementation of European priorities, such as the Green Deal.

Activities

Our web search and initial survey resulted in an overview of a myriad of activities in Public Engagement. In this section we will try to order these roughly in line with the Ladder of Participation. Because of the different institutional and national contexts of these activities, and resulting differences, this is a challenge.

The current overview is obviously incomplete, but aims to inspire, identify options for mutual learning and collaboration, and the listing can be updated throughout the project.

Outreach Activities

Most universities have implemented outreach programmes which focus on attracting future students (which is an additional incentive for them to employ these activities). These programmes can range from pure marketing to science communication and PER-activities; either focusing very direct on the target groups (final years secondary school) or on younger children and their parents (creating a scientific culture). Parts of these activities can fall under the heading of 'public engagement'. Next to the already mentioned structures in the previous chapter, the table below highlights a few of these activities.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UGent	Educational activities and tools for pupils and teachers	School Support	Department of Communication and Marketing	educatiefaanbod.ugent.be/nl
RUG	Discovery Truck	Mobile Science Centre for Outreach	Science LinX	www.jouwenergievanmor-gen.nl/
	Education program primary schools	Outreach	Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health	www.rug.nl/aletta/public-engagement/ern-2021/education-programme
UGOE	School Laboratory and Children University	Outreach		uni-goettingen.de/de/586256.html

Table 7. Outreach activities in ENLIGHT

Online Information Services

These can be social media channels on which there is more than just a one-way flow of information. If people can respond to messages, share, like, a form of engagement develops. These activities could emerge to become online discussion forums.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UGent	durfdenken.be	Website	Department of Communication and Marketing	www.durfdenken.be/en/research-and-society
	FUTUREproef		Green Office	futureproef.ugent.be
UPV/EHU	Mapping Ignorance	Blog	Chair of Scientific Culture	mappingignorance.org
	Mujeres con Ciencia	Online Information	Chair of Scientific Culture	mujeresconciencia.com
	Cuaderno de Cultura Científica	Online Information	Chair of Scientific Culture	culturacientifica.com
	Zientzia Kaiera	Online Information	Chair of Scientific Culture	zientziakaiera.eus
UT	Corona Conference	Information on Corona Research (Online)	All Faculties	koroonaKonverents.ut.ee/
UU	Crush Covid	Information on Corona Infection Numbers (website); does make use of volunteers who report on their own status in an app	Medical Sciences	crush-covid.shinyapps.io/crush_covid/

Table 8. Online Information Services in ENLIGHT

Public Lectures/Informal Dialogue Events

Many ENLIGHT partners organize public lectures, after which there is time for Q&A. In some cases, there is more emphasis on dialogue, such as in Science Café's. These are also quite common now in the portfolio of public engagement activities (not all are mentioned in the table below).

A Science Café is an event organised in an informal setting as a place of dialogue with participants coming from all walks of life and academia. An expert presents a subject in a concise and open manner after which the floor is open for a discussion. The moderator facilitates the sharing of a wide range of views on the subject at hand. The University of Ghent organizes two variants; the Science Bar is focused on secondary school students.

Other interesting variants are a Talk show at the University of Groningen, a weekly online conversation at the University of Uppsala and a conference series of the University of Göttingen (though the latter is more focused on the professional community).

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UGent	Science bar	Science Café	Science Communication Unit	www.sciencebar.be
	Science cafes	Science Café	Science Communication Unit	www.wetenschapscafe.be
RUG	Aletta's keuken	Talk show.	Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health	www.rug.nl/aletta/public-engagement/ern-2021/alettas-keuken
	Public Academy for Law	Public Lectures	Law Faculty	www.rug.nl/rechten/recht-en-samenleving/publieksacademie
UU	Upptalk Weekly	Online Conversation	Faculty for Science and Technology	www.upptech.uu.se/upptalk-weekly
UGOE	Science for Peace and Sustainability	Conference Series	Public Relations Department / Third Mission + Green Office division	www.uni-goettingen.de/en/conferences+series+/632130.html

Table 9. Public Lectures/Informal Dialogues in ENLIGHT

Science Festivals/Exhibitions

Many ENLIGHT partners are active in Science Festivals. These can be small or large, short or long, and are sometimes part of European events, such as European Researchers Night, or connected to local cultural festivals.

During these festivals there is usually a range of activities, from showcasing research results or equipment (lectures, exhibits, shows), workshops for kids, or informal dialogues.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UGent	Participation in the 'Day of Science' (Dag van de Wetenschap)	Science Festival	Science Communication Unit	www.dagvandewetenschap.be
UPV/EHU	Naukas Bilbao	Science Festival	Chair of Scientific Culture	bzp.eus
RUG	Chronically Healthy	Traveling interactive exhibition	Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health	www.rug.nl/aletta/public-engagement/exhibition-little-troublemakers
	Weekend of Science	Science Festival	Many Departments	
UPV/EHU	European Researchers' Night	Science Festival	Office of the University	www.ikertzaiengaua-ehu.org/hasiera/
	Zientzia Astea (Science Week)	Science Festival	Office of the University	zientzia-astea.org/es/
UU	SciFest	Science Festival	Domain of Science and Technology	www.scifest.se
UGOE	Night of Science	Science Festival	Public Relations Department / Third Mission + Green Office division	https://www.goettinger-nacht-des-wissens.de

Table 10. Science Festivals/Exhibitions of ENLIGHT

Consultancy Services

Next to the aforementioned consultancy through Science Shops and similar, there are a number of other interesting activities within ENLIGHT. The University of Tartu swiftly set up information service on COVID, and one professor offered to test the reliability of facemasks, which people could send to his lab.

Uppsala University has set-up Aim-day (Academy-Industry Meeting Day) in which however every type of organisation can submit a problem to discuss with academics in a one-hour meeting, and thus get a number of possibilities to consider.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UT	Ask the researcher (COVID)	Online Interaction	Researcher with support from Communication Team	www.facebook.com/events/502278297429525/?acontext=%7B%22event_action_history%22%3A%7B%22surface%22%3A%22page%22%7D%7D
	Mask testing	Free testing of face masks	Environmental Physics in UT	atmos.ut.ee/en/masks/maskitabel/
UU	Aimday	Online Consultancy	Innovation Partnership Office	www.aimday.se

Table 11. Consultancy activities of ENLIGHT

Hackathons etc.

A hackathon is an event in which teams of participants work non-stop to come up with solutions for cases presented within a short period of time. Challenge prizes offer a reward to whoever can first or most effectively meet a defined challenge. They act as an incentive for addressing a specific problem, rather than being a reward for past achievements. A challenge prize can incentivise innovation, focus attention on a particular issue and unlock financing and other resources.

University of Bordeaux reported two different types of hackathons; one to edit Wikipedia pages with reports on university research, and a climate problems hackathon.

A lighter version of a hackathon is a contest, such as the video contest of the University of the Basque Country, where participants are challenged to explain a scientific phenomenon in a video clip.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UBx	Wikipedia Editathon	Online Science Communication	University Library	fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Projet:Ma_These_Wikipedia_Et_Moi
	Climackathon	Hackathon	Innovation Department and TRUST (department in charge of sustainability and social responsibility)	www.u-bordeaux.fr/Actualites/De-la-vie-de-campus/Climackathon-une-premiere-edition-reussie
UPV/EHU	Ciencia Clip	Video Contest	Chair of Scientific Culture	cienciaclip.naukas.com

Table 12. Hackathons and similar in ENLIGHT

Service Learning

Service-learning is an educational approach that combines learning objectives with community service in order to provide a pragmatic, progressive learning experience while meeting societal needs (*Wikipedia*). These projects aim to have mutual benefit; for the students and the community involved. It can be voluntary (as e.g. at University of Bordeaux) or as part of the curriculum (such as in Ghent and Galway).

They are different from Science Shop projects in a sense that Service Learning does not necessarily involve research.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UBx	Services civiques	Student Volunteering		www.u-bordeaux.fr/Campus/Emplois-etudiants
UGent	Community Service Learning	Service Learning	Department of Educational Policy	www.ugent.be/community-service-learning
NUIG	Service Learning	Service Learning	Community Knowledge Initiative	stories.nuigalway.ie/service-learning/index.html

Table 13. Service Learning in ENLIGHT

Citizen Science Projects

Citizen Science is the inclusion of lay persons in scientific research, usually by collecting or analysing data as part of a scientific project. Citizens are actively engaged in scientific work, so that scientific research is being done by the citizen and not just for the citizen. Nowadays Citizen Science is an organized, and in many cases hierarchical, process meaning that citizen science projects are mostly (not necessarily) initiated and supervised by professional scientists.

Citizen Science projects are carried out for research that affords a great number of spatially dispersed contributions (such as for weather or environmental observations) or involves a great amount of tedious work that does not necessarily involve expert knowledge (in some citizen science projects, citizens can be involved in more stages of the research process, up to 'extreme citizen science' which includes them in all stages). 'Participatory Sensing' is one of the ways to do Citizen Science, facilitated with ICT platforms which often include the use of hand-held devices such as smartphones. In its broadest sense, participatory mapping means the creation of maps by local communities – often with the involvement of supporting organisations including governments, NGOs or other actors engaged in development or land-related planning. ENLIGHT actors are active in a variety of Citizen Science projects. These all engage with citizens in various phases of the research, to various degrees.

Some projects use citizens as voluntary research *objects*, and as a consequence, these projects are sometimes excluded from what is called Citizen Science (as the citizens are passive in this case). However, such projects do need active engagement with society in order to keep volunteers attracted and informed. An example is the *Speech lab* at University of Groningen, that collects different dialects and accents. Another example

is the *Crush-Covid* project at the University of Uppsala, in which citizens report on their own status.

Other projects actively share project outcomes and involve citizens / volunteers to create impact (such as the *Bees and Fish project* of Comenius University).

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UBx	SPINE	Citizen Science	Labex TRAIL and Innovation Department	ourspinelab.u-bordeaux.fr/login
UBx & UPV/EHU	Oceani3: BLUE SKILLS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BLUE ECONOMY IN THE BASQUE-AQUITAINE CROSS-BORDER COASTLINE	Citizen Science	DIPE - Direction of partnerships and innovation	oceani3.com/en/inicio-english/
UGent	Citizen Science Projects	Citizen Science	Individual Researchers	www.ugent.be/nl/onderzoek/maatschappij/citizen-science.htm
CU	Occurrence of the Aesculapian snake in Bratislava	Citizen Science	Faculty of Natural Sciences	www.facebook.com/ZamenisBA/
	Conservation of European Ground Squirrel	Citizen Science	Faculty of Natural Sciences	broz.sk/en/projekty/conservation-of-european-ground-squirrel/
	Bees and Fish Project	Communication of results	Faculty of natural Sciences (partner in international project)	broz.sk/en/projekty/beesandfish/
RUG	Speech Lab	<i>Makes use of volunteers as research object</i>	Faculty of Arts	www.rug.nl/let/spraaklab
	CurioUs	Citizen Science	Science LinX, Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health and Forum Groningen	forum.nl/curious

UU	Crush Covid	<i>does make use of volunteers who report on their own status in an app</i>	Medical Sciences	crush-covid.shinyapps.io/crush_covid/
UT	Estonia/Europe is searching for cowslips	Citizen Science	Landscape biodiversity research group at the Faculty of Ecology and Earth Sciences	landscape.ut.ee/what-we-do/citizen-science-campaign/?lang=en

Table 14. Citizen Science activities in ENLIGHT

Co-creation alliances/Living Labs/User Committees

Next to the multi-disciplinary schools or e.g. the projects of Science Shops, there are more public engagement activities that focus on co-creation.

Living Labs use an actual place and its users to together solve issues, such as sustainability, in an action research way. An example is the project at the Campus of the University of the Basque Country, called Campus Bizia Lab (Living Campus Laboratory). The University of Bordeaux is currently in the process of establishing three living labs: urban forest, air quality, and resilient habitat; a living lab on mobility is under study.

A user committee is another way to guarantee usability of research and innovation output, and use practical experience in the innovation process; not only in industrial innovation but also for innovation of social processes, such as teaching. This is for instance done in a project at Comenius University, where teachers actively participate in the development of teaching materials.

The Prevention Accelerator of the University of Groningen is another such activity, which supports good ideas in preventive health care to become widely applicable and available.

University	Activity	Type	Unit	
UPV/EHU	Campus Bizia Lab	Living Lab	Direction of Sustainability and Social Commitment	www.ehu.eus/en/web/iraunkortasuna/campus-bizia-lab
CU	Support for teacher education	User Committee	Faculty of Mathematics, physics and informatics	

RUG	Prevention Accelerator	Co-Creation	Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health	www.preventieversneller.nl
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Table 15. Co-creation alliances/Living Labs/User Committees in ENLIGHT

Concluding remarks

The tables above shed a first light on the variety of activities among the ENLIGHT partners. The way these activities are embedded and funded is quite different among the partners and depends on local/national context.

Within ENLIGHT universities, providing the best education and career perspectives for our students is a priority. Simultaneously, students offer an enormous resource for engaging with the public. In many cases this can lead to a win-win situation, in which both the student and the public (or civil society in general) benefits.

Students can participate in various engagement activities as part of their curriculum. This is most prominent in Service Learning and projects for Science Shops. However, also Living Labs, Citizen Science projects and research projects in Interdisciplinary Research Schools offer these opportunities in general.

For activities where there is less formal 'learning' for students, we noticed that students are hired (as Student-Assistant or intern). In this case, they are more comparable to facilitators of public engagement, or junior staff. This is most prominent in outreach activities. However, it is worth mentioning that students are voluntarily involved in some activities as well.

Follow-up

Based on the findings from our initial survey, we are planning to organize a series of online workshops with the contact persons of the ENLIGHT universities. The main purpose of these will be to showcase and discuss which public engagement structures or activities ENLIGHT-RISE partners would like to strengthen.

This will lead to a mentoring programme, in which experts from one partner can advise others, and in which joint workshops/trainings or information exchanges can be facilitated. In addition, we expect ideas for joint projects to be developed during this programme.

Also, we aim to investigate how to make our data available in a searchable format, with added details and contact persons listed for internal use within ENLIGHT. For this, we will collaborate with those responsible for some of the other work packages in ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT-RISE.

Finally, we will probably need an adapted, simpler version of the questionnaire to remain open during the project, to complete the overview of structures and activities, and keep it up to date. It may also be useful to make simple survey to check within each partner university, to find out who else is active in (or interested in) public engagement. This would then have to be administered by the individual partners themselves, to create an internal public engagement network.

Appendix I.

Short background ENLIGHT & ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT is a European university Network to promote equitable quality of Life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher education Transformation. It brings together 9 comprehensive, research-intensive, new flagship universities with a strong reputation. ENLIGHT strives to transform the way in which we address global societal challenges by developing new models and methodologies for education and research adapted to the complex sustainability issues facing cities and communities today.; ENLIGHT focuses on five flagship challenges: Health & Well-being, Climate change, Energy & Circular Economy, Digital Revolution and Equity. With ENLIGHT RISE (Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty) we will support ENLIGHT in its R&I dimension, to deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda, in synergy with the educational component, in partnership with surrounding ecosystems, and with the overarching goal of serving our societal missions. The objective is to become more competitive and innovative together, leveraging and synergizing our respective strengths and capitalizing on our innovation potential and partnerships with our surrounding ecosystems to jointly promote a greener, healthier, more equitable and sustainable Europe. To reach these goals, ENLIGHT RISE will 1- establish a longer term business model for joint R&I actions, 2- identify strong research synergies with high innovation potential 3- enable the sharing of and optimize capacity or digital research infrastructures, while benchmarking and optimizing the societal impact of digital innovation/artificial intelligence, 4- *reinforce cooperation and co-creation with the business sector and civil society*, 5- *mainstream and incentivize open science practices and public engagement*, 6- improve the attractiveness of researchers' careers, and 7- develop and formalize methods towards an impact-driven R&I agenda.

Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
National University of Ireland, Galway	NUI Galway	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

Appendix II.

Glossary for Types of Engagement (Send as background Information with the Survey)

Online interactive medium / Deliberative online forum

These can be social media channels on which there is interaction, on which people can respond to messages, share, like, etc. They can also be focused online discussion forums.

Advise / Consultancy / Equipment service

These can consist of question-and-answer websites/phones, consultation hours, support for school pupils with their school projects, library/literature access, access to or lending of equipment, methodological support (there is an overlap with other type of activities, such as the science shop).

(Deliberative) Poll / (group) Interviews / Focus Groups / Consensus Workshop – Consensus Conference / Scenario Workshop / Delphi Method / World Café / Futures Workshop

These are public engagement tools to find out the opinion of people on research (could be on research questions, goals, approach, ethics, usability, impacts).

Advisory Panel / User Committee

These are public engagement tools to make sure that the opinion and needs of people are reflected in the research.

Public Lecture + Discussion

These are publicly accessible lectures that allow for question-and-answer sessions.

(interactive) Science Theatre

Science Theatre can be used to e.g. magnify ethical dilemmas of research and interact with the audience, create awareness and stir public discussion.

Science Café

A Science Café is an event organised in an informal setting as a place of dialogue with participants coming from all walks of life and academia. An expert presents a subject in a concise and open manner after which the floor is open for a discussion. The moderator facilitates the sharing of a wide range of views on the subject at hand.

Reverse Science Café

A 'reverse science café' has the public speaking, or at least taking their issue as a starting point, and has the researchers asking questions / responding to the public / intending to learn. It's a variant made popular during the European SPARKS-project⁸.

Hackathon / Challenge

A hackathon is an event in which teams of participants work non-stop to come up with solutions for cases presented within a short period of time. Challenge prizes offer a reward to whoever can first or most effectively meet a defined challenge. They act as an incentive for addressing a specific problem, rather than being a reward for past achievements. A challenge prize can incentivise innovation, focus attention on a particular issue and unlock financing and other resources.

Interactive Exhibit(ion)

Exhibits or exhibitions can create interactivity; between visitor and exhibit or among visitors.

Fablab / Makerspace / Repair Café

A FabLab offers access to the use of e.g. 3D printers and other technical tools. A makerspace is a collaborative work space inside a school, library or separate public/private facility for making, learning, exploring and sharing that uses high tech to no tech tools. In a repair café, the public gets support to repair their own equipment, to prevent it going to waste.

Participatory Design

Participatory design can be done together with citizens concerned about a certain issue (e.g. the environment). The starting point is consultation with individuals and

⁸ <https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/projects/sparks>

community organisations. This is followed by an interactive design process which includes field tests with the users of the developed technologies and devices.

Citizen Science / Participatory Sensing / Participatory Mapping

Citizen Science is the inclusion of lay persons in scientific research, usually by collecting or analysing data as part of a scientific project. Citizens are actively engaged in scientific work, so that scientific research is being done by the citizen and not just for the citizen. Nowadays Citizen Science is an organized, and in many cases hierarchical, process meaning that citizen science projects are mostly (not necessarily) initiated and supervised by professional scientists. Citizen Science projects are carried out for research that affords a great number of spatially dispersed contributions (such as for weather or environmental observations) or involves a great amount of tedious work that does not necessarily involve expert knowledge (in some citizen science projects, citizens can be involved in more stages of the research process, up to 'extreme citizen science' which includes them in all stages). 'Participatory Sensing' is one of the ways to do Citizen Science, facilitated with ICT platforms which often include the use of hand-held devices such as smartphones. In its broadest sense, participatory mapping means the creation of maps by local communities – often with the involvement of supporting organisations including governments, NGOs or other actors engaged in development or land-related planning. More about Citizen Science [here](#).

Service Learning

Service-learning is an educational approach that combines learning objectives with community service in order to provide a pragmatic, progressive learning experience while meeting societal needs (*Wikipedia*).

Science Shop

Students and researchers do research requested by Civil Society Organizations (CSOs). The research project is defined together based on the CSOs needs. The CSO can have varying degrees of involvement in the actual research process. The results of the research are made public. The service is usually free of charge and students do the research as part of their curriculum. More information about Science Shops is available via [Living Knowledge](#), the international network of [science shops](#).

(Community-based) Participatory Action Research

The community is involved in (all) stages of the research process, from setting the questions, to framing and doing the research, interpreting the results and communication. Research is focused on better understanding and then improving a

certain situation. If combined with actions to implement findings, this leads to a cycle of participatory action research

Appendix III.

The initial survey

The survey was accompanied by an invitation explaining the work package, and gave the background on Public Engagement similar as in the introduction to this report. In addition, we gave these instructions to respondents. The survey form is at the end of this appendix.

1) Please fill-out a google form for each PER/collaborative research activity at your university. You can send this to the people at your institute whom you know to be active in Public Engagement with Research or closely related activities (see also next page for activities we have already found on your websites). You may want to underscore the importance of the ENLIGHT projects for your institute when asking your colleagues.

At this stage , getting a quick overview is most important; we can always contact the persons involved in the activity for further details if you/they don't know exact answers: (LINK DELETED) In the form (see below), we will ask you to indicate in which phase of the research process there is engagement

A: agenda setting

B: data collection

C: data analysis

D: discussing outcomes of research

E: implementing research outcomes/creating impact

We will also ask you to indicate level of engagement

0 = informing (no engagement)

1 = responding to questions / informal dialogue

3 = consulting, asking opinions

4 = involving

5 = full collaboration

A glossary of Public Engagement tools/methods/structures is at the end of this document.

In the survey, you can tick a box to indicate what type of activity applies. **You can leave**

this blank if you don't know; we will sort it later – or add a new category. (the following includes information derived from *Engage2020* and its [action catalogue](#)) I attach 4 examples of answers to the survey questions.

2) Secondly, please send us links to those sections of strategic plans (of your university or a separate faculty) dealing with outreach, public engagement, collaboration with civil society, etc. (by mail to XXXXXXXXXX)

Below is an example of information from a strategic plan. These excerpts from strategic plans can give us some guidance on how to move forward in advancing PER at the various ENLIGHT partners.

Strategic Plan (example)

RUG : making Connections (2021-2026) www.rug.nl/about-ug/policy-and-strategy/strategic-plan/

Corner stone (p3): to stimulate learning and research in an interdisciplinary setting **with and for regional**, European and global **partners** to find sustainable, innovative solutions to the challenges that society faces;

Societal Impact (p15-20): *working together with and for society*. In order to realise our responsibility towards society, we are intensifying our contribution to the resolution of societal issues, in particular those in the Northern Netherlands, through our education and research.

What we have found in a quick search on your websites.

This is probably incomplete; there may be more activities that we did not find on the website or activities that are done but not mentioned.

Bordeaux: [University Foundation](#) (but unclear if there is any engagement other than economic or governmental actors involved) / **["services civiques"](#) (voluntary)**

Ghent: [student challenges](#) / [collaboration master thesis](#) / [internships](#) / [events](#)

Bratislava: **participation in** "science cafés" or "science fairs", even though these are not directly university events. Noc Výskumníkov: www.nocvyskumnikov.sk/european-researchers-night.html and Týždeň Vedy a Techniky: www.tyzdenvedy.sk/information-in-english.html?page_id=342; scientists from our CU inform the general public about Corona-19 from their research field point of view vedapomaha.sk/.

Uppsala: (only [collaborations with business and industry](#))?

Galway: [Community Engagement](#) (broad portfolio)

Tartu: (only [Business/Entrepreneurship](#))?

Göttingen: "[Forum Knowledge](#)" / [For Pupils](#) / [Events](#)

Basque Country: zientzia.info/en/ / www.ehu.eus/es/web/ehugune and participations (Scientific activities promoted by the Research Vice Rectorate <http://zientzia-astea.org/es/> (science week); www.ikertzaileengaua-ehu.org/ (European researchers night) there are also groups/organisations formed by people from our university that do some kind of PE in collaboration with other groups:<http://crystalclear.es/> ; ekopol.eus/)

Groningen: [Society](#) (broad portfolio: science shops, info desk high school students; collaboration centre for elementary schools; studium generale – debates, public lectures, science cafés; "public academies (law, medicine); university museum with educational programmes/events/guided tours; / [Science LinX \(STEM-PE\)](#) / [Aletta Jacobs School of Public Health](#) (health-PE)

FORM:

Please, fill out one form per activity. JUST LEAVE BLANK WHERE YOU DON'T KNOW. We will sort that out later. Don't worry about mistakes either. For any questions, mail to (MAIL address deleted) Thanks!!

* Required

1. Email *
2. University *
3. Name of the activity
4. Short Objective of the Activity
5. Website
6. Contact details/person
7. Which unit within the university is responsible? Could be a faculty, department, office, centre, etc. (NOTE If there is an external partner organizing this activity, and the university is (only) a 'participant' in the activity, please describe this
8. The activity is (Mark only one oval):
 - Fully embedded in the university structure / strategy / Continuous Embedded on a project basis / Temporary

- Individual activity (with some support, or as part of official obligation for academic staff)
 - Individual activity, voluntary
 - Other:
9. Who are involved internally? Check all that apply.
- Researchers/Professors/Teachers Support Staff
 - Students (voluntary)
 - Students (in curriculum/for credits)
 - Students (paid)
 - Directors/Policy makers of university or department
 - Other:
10. Who are external target groups/partners? Check all that apply.
- Civil Society Organizations / Community Groups Non-profit organizations
 - Citizens (in general)
 - Affected Citizens specifically (can include Patients, vulnerable populations, etc)
 - Citizens as (Potential) Users / Consumers
 - Employees Pupils / Schools
 - Municipalities / Local Public Agencies
 - Other:
11. Involvement in which part(s) of the research process? Check all that apply.
- Agenda setting
 - Data collection
 - Data analysis
 - Discussing outcomes of research
 - Implementing research outcomes/creating impact
 - Other:
12. Level of engagement (tick most appropriate option). Mark only one oval.
- informing (no engagement)
 - responding to questions / informal dialogue
 - consulting, asking for opinions of external actors involving
 - full collaboration
 - don't know
 - Other:
13. Type of activity (or similar to) Check all that apply.
- Online interactive medium
 - Advise / Consultancy service
 - Poll / (group) Interviews / Focus Groups / Consensus Workshop / Scenario Workshop / Delphi Rounds / World Café / Futures Workshop
 - Advisory Panel / User Committee

- Public Lecture + Discussion
 - (interactive) Science Theatre
 - Science Café
 - Reverse Science Café
 - Hackathon / Challenge
 - Interactive Exhibit(ion)
 - Fablab / Makerspace / Repair Café
 - Participatory Design
 - Citizen Science / Participatory Sensing / Participatory Mapping
 - Service Learning
 - Science Shop
 - Participatory Action Research
 - Other:
14. Funding comes from
 15. Long description of the activity
 16. Additional remarks / Questions

Appendix IV.

Links to current strategic plans of the partner universities

	Strategic plan	Public engagement
UBx	idex.u-bordeaux.fr/files/IdEx/U25 Strategic Plan - december 2015.pdf	
UGent	www.ugent.be/en/research/science-society/impact/soc-impact.htm	
RUG	www.rug.nl/about-ug/policy-and-strategy/strategic-plan/	p.3, p.15-20
UPV/EHU	www.ehu.es/documents/2921104/26237464/Research+Plan+19-22.pdf/e8480ef7-91f2-f619-d413-0f474f7a31f3?t=1608548175265 (Pdf)	
CU	uniba.sk/fileadmin/ruk/legislativa/2021/dlhodoby_zamer rozvoja UK 2021-2027.pdf (in national language)	
NUIG	www.nuigalway.ie/media/strategicplanning/NUI-Galway-Strategy-2020-2025---Shared-Vision,-Shaped-by-Values.pdf	
UT	ut.ee/en/strategic-plan-2025	P. 12
UU	regler.uu.se/digitalAssets/14/c_14263-l_1-k_c_14263-l_1-k_uppsala-university---mission--goals-and-strategies.pdf	
UGOE	www.uni-goettingen.de/en/625860.html	